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	Total	1048	28	23	30	22	17	120	0	1168
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☐ 2 Note on inversion temperature in pinning of vortices by peri...	1978	2						0		2
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☐ 6 Vortices in inhomogeneous superconductors with periodically ...	1984	6						0		6
☐ 7 Commensurate-incommensurate phase coexistence in physisorbed...	1984	3						0		3
☐ 8 Orientational instability of higher-order commensurate latti...	1984							0		0
☐ 9 Citical temperature of superconductor/ferromagnet superlatti...	1987	6						0		6

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☐	11	Upper critical fields of superconductor-ferromagnet multilay...	1988	137	1		1	1	3		140
☐	12	Field structure of vortex lattices in uniaxial superconducto...	1989	92	2	1	1	1	5		97
☐	13	Transition temperatures of superconductor-ferromagnet superl...	1991	296	2	2	3	4	14	3	310
☐	14	Phase diagram of superconductingnormal-metal superlattices	1991	11		1			1		12
☐	15	Vortex and nonvortex nucleation of superconductivity in ferr...	1991	10					0		10
☐	16	Phase diagram of superconductor-ferromagnet superlattices	1991	7		1			1		8
☐	17	Magnetic field dependence of the critical currents in high T...	1991	5				1	1		6
☐	18	Vortices in anisotropic type-II superconductors	1992	6					0		6
☐	19	Critical currents in superconductor-normal metal-superconduc...	1993	5			1	2	3		8
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☐	21	Flux penetration and pinning in superconductor-ferromagnet s...	1994						0		0
☐	22	Influence of exchange field on d-wave superconductivity	1996						0		0
☐	23	Quasiparticle spectrum of vortices in cuprates	1998						0		0
☐	24	Critical field of thin superconducting cylinders	1998						0		0
☐	25	Spontaneous currents in josephson devices	1998						0		0
☐	26	Bound states in the vortex core	1998						0		0
☐	27	Phase-dependent energy spectrum in josephson weak links	1999	14				1	1		15
☐	28	Spontaneous currents in Josephson devices	1999	6			1		1		7
☐	29	Quasiparticle excitation spectrum of an isolated vortex in a...	1999	1	1				1		2
☐	30	Spin paramagnetism in d-wave superconductors	2000						0		0
☐	31	Andreev bound states in superconductor/ferromagnet junctions	2000						0		0
☐	32	Spontaneous currents in superconductor-ferromagnet devices	2000						0		0
☐	33	Quasiparticle energy spectrum in ferromagnetic Josephson wea...	2000	9				1	1		10
☐	34	Zero-energy states in s-wave/normal-metal/d-wave superconduc...	2001	2					0		2
☐	35	Coexistence of stable and metastable 0 and π states in Josep...	2001	55			2	1	3		58
☐	36	Coherent effects in double-barrier ferromagnet/superconducto...	2002	4	2		1	1	4		8
☐	37	Coherent effects in double-barrier ferromagnet/superconducto...	2002	52	1	1		1	3		55
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☐	39	Josephson effect in double-barrier superconductor-ferromagne...	2003	79	4	1	1	2	8		87
☐	40	Coherent electronic transport through a superconducting film	2003						0		0
☐	41	Ferromagnet-superconductor proximity effect: The clean limit	2005	11	1		1		2		13
☐	42	Quasiparticle states in superconducting superlattices	2005	3					0		3
☐	43	Resonant amplification of the Andreev process in short Josep...	2005						0		0
☐	44	Erratum: Coherent effects in double-barrier ferromagnet/supe...	2005	2			1	1	2		4
☐	45	Josephson coupling through ferromagnetic heterojunctions wit...	2006	38	2	1	1	1	7	2	45
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☐	49	Ballistic transport in ferromagnet-superconductor-ferromagne...	2007	3	1	1	1		3		6

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☐	50	Bistability in superconducting rings containing an inhomogen...	2008							0		0
☐	51	Photoinduced expansion of cuprate superconductors: Evidence ...	2008	22	2	1			1	4		26
☐	52	Madelung strain in cuprate superconductors - A route to enha...	2009	11	2	3	1		1	7		18
☐	53	Insights in high-temperature superconductivity from the stud...	2009	7				1		1		8
☐	54	Resonant effects in ballistic josephson junctions	2009				2			2		2
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☐	56	Influence of different band masses on ballistic charge trans...	2009							0		0
☐	57	Josephson effect and triplet pairing in SFFS junctions	2010							0		0
☐	58	Long-range spin-triplet proximity effect in Josephson juncti...	2010	35		2	1	3	1	7		42
☐	59	Comprehensive study of high- T_c interface supercon...	2010	4						0		4
☐	60	Josephson effect and spin-triplet pairing correlations in SF...	2011	40	1	2	3	1	1	8		48
☐	61	Signature of the long range triplet proximity effect in the ...	2012	11					2	2		13
☐	62	Anomalous independence of interface superconductivity from c...	2013	24	5	5	8	2	2	22		46
☐	63	Early stages of magnetization relaxation in superconductors	2013	7	1					1		8
☐	64	Interface Superconductivity in Cuprates Defies Fermi-Liquid ...	2017				1		1	2		2
☐	65	Interference phenomena in Josephson junctions with ferromagn...	2022							0		0

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